

Menopause averted a midlife energetic crisis with help from older children and parents: A simulation study

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Abstract The grandmother hypothesis is the most influential account of the evolution of menopause in humans, but other theories warrant investigation. Here I use simulations to investigate two theories that ground the evolution of menopause in biparental care. Kaplan et al. (2010) proposed a “two-sex” learning and skill-based account, termed the *Embodied Capital Model* (ECM), in which the high energetic burden of caring for multiple, slow-developing offspring was met with biparental investment. Menopause evolved because the physiological costs of pregnancy and childbirth increased with age yet productivity also increased with age, and the benefits of transferring resources to adult children and their offspring eventually outweigh the benefits of continued reproduction. Kuhle (2007) proposed the “father absent” hypothesis in which the higher mortality rate of husbands would often have left wives without the resources to raise young children, selecting for early reproductive cessation in monogamous couples. Simulations of hunter-gatherer energy consumption and production across the lifespan, taking account of age- and sex-specific survivorship, interbirth intervals, and varying rates of strength and foraging skill acquisition typical of contemporary foragers, reveal a pronounced midlife energy deficit that could be averted by ceasing reproduction midlife and receiving energy transfers from both younger couples (e.g., brideservice) and from older parents (the grandmother hypothesis). Menopause emerges as an integral and strictly necessary component of the unique human pattern of relatively short interbirth intervals and a long period of juvenile dependency, supporting and extending the ECM. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18149332](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18149332)

1 Introduction

Prolonged post-reproductive lifespans are rare in wild animals (Chapman et al., 2024; Ellis, Franks, Nattress, Cant, et al., 2018; Monaghan & Ivimey-Cook, 2023; cf. Winkler & Goncalves,

2023), which is consistent with the expectation that somatic and reproductive functions should senesce at similar rates (Croft et al., 2015). The explanation for the oddly long post-reproductive lifespans of females in humans and a few other species, on the other hand, remains hotly debated (see Figure 1). In brief, byproduct or non-adaptive explanations include that these are artifacts of unusually benign environments (e.g., captivity, recent improvements in public health) that extend lifespan but not fertility; that these are epiphenomena of antagonistic pleiotropy; or that these are artifacts of selection for male longevity that extended female lifespan but not fertility.

Adaptive explanations include the influential grandmother hypothesis, in which the benefits of investing in grandchildren outweighed the fitness benefits of producing more children; the mother hypothesis, in which the benefits of maintaining investment in multiple slow-developing offspring outweighed the increasing risk of maternal morbidity and mortality from continued reproduction; the “aging eggs” hypothesis, in which increased risk of chromosomal abnormalities selected for a cessation of reproduction; and the avoidance of breeding competition with genetic kin. These and other hypotheses have been extensively reviewed elsewhere (Arnot, 2021; Croft et al., 2015; Ellis et al., 2024; Hawkes, 2020; Holmes, 2019; Monaghan & Ivimey-Cook, 2023; Peccei, 2001; Sievert, 2024), so I will not revisit them here. Instead, I will further develop two related hypotheses for the evolution of human menopause that have received relatively little attention.

Figure 1: Post-reproductive lifespans of humans, African great apes and other primates, and toothed whales. Values represent the life expectancy from the end of the fertile period as a proportion of life expectancy from the beginning of the fertile period. Human and nonhuman primate values are from Wood et al. (2023), except for the largest gorilla value, which is from Smit & Robbins (2025). Toothed whale values are from Ellis, Franks, Natrass, Currie, et al. (2018).

1.1 The “two-sex” embodied capital model of menopause

Kaplan et al. (2010) proposed a “two-sex” learning and skill-based model of the evolution of human menopause. In this account, humans evolved to exploit a highly knowledge- and skill-based “niche” providing energy-rich but difficult to extract resources that required the rearing of slow-developing, large-brained offspring (Kaplan et al., 2000). Offspring were produced every few years but required almost two decades to become self-sufficient, placing a potentially high

energetic burden on mothers. This burden is met by a co-evolving sexual division of labor in long-term monogamous marriages in which husbands specialized in skill-based acquisition of high-risk, high-return resources, with their skills and productivity increasing for about two decades beyond the age at which they became self-sufficient. Mothers specialized in child rearing and acquisition of lower-risk, lower-return resources. Menopause evolved because the physiological costs of pregnancy and childbirth increased with age, and oocyte quality decreased with age, yet productivity also increased with age. In this scenario, around midlife the fitness benefits of downward intergenerational transfers of resources by both parents, whose acquisition was based on four decades of skill development, termed *embodied capital*, outweighed the fitness benefits of continued offspring production. This account is part of the highly influential *Embodied Capital Model* (ECM, Kaplan et al., 2000). See Figure 2.

Figure 2: Energy production and consumption curves. **A, B:** Mean daily energy consumption and production for male and female hunter-gatherers and chimpanzees. Figures from Kaplan et al. (2000). **C:** Parental production, children's demands, and net family production, observed Tsimane pattern. **D:** Simulation based on delayed menopause. Figures from Kaplan et al. (2010).

1.2 The absent father model of menopause

Kuhle (2007) proposed a two-part “absent father” hypothesis for the evolution of menopause in humans that assumes the evolutionary importance of a sexual division of labor in long-term marriages, similar to the scenario proposed by Kaplan and colleagues (Kaplan et al., 2010, 2000). The first part proposes that fathers who abandoned their wives for younger women would have left their ex-wives without “the necessary level of paternal investment to rear newborns to reproductive age” (p. 332). The second part proposes that because male mortality is greater than female mortality, and because husbands tend to be older than their wives, husbands would often have died before their wives, again leaving the wives without the resources necessary to rear newborns. Unlike the more influential mother and grandmother hypotheses, the Kaplan et al. (2010) and Kuhle (2007) hypotheses both propose that a sexual division of labor in long-term monogamous relationships played a central role in the evolution of human menopause.

Although serial monogamy is not uncommon in the ethnographic record, Kaplan et al. (2010) emphasize the cost of mate-switching, and provide evidence that in small scale societies most children are produced and raised in long-term monogamous relationships. I will therefore set the wife abandonment hypothesis aside and focus on the “two sex” aspect of the Kaplan et al. (2010) and Kuhle (2007) hypotheses.

1.3 New data on the ontogeny of foraging skills

The ECM, based on the data available at the time, emphasized that adult men produced a substantial surplus of energy from high return but difficult to acquire resources, with maximum production around age 35-40, reproductive aged women produced approximately their own daily total energy expenditure (TEE), and post-reproductive women produced a modest surplus (Gurven et al., 2006; Kaplan et al., 2000; Walker et al., 2002). These surpluses supported a growing family of slowly developing offspring, each of whom would require energetic subsidies for up to 20 years. See Figure 2A,B.

Subsequently, two important sets of empirical results suggest a modification of the ECM might be necessary. First, in many populations proficiency in hunting and other food production occurs earlier in adulthood, and is more constant throughout adulthood, than depicted for men in Figure 2A. A study of hunting based on ~23,000 records from more than 1800 individuals from 40 locations, for example – mostly men – found that skill and productivity increased more rapidly with age than envisioned in the ECM, peaking in the early 30’s, and remaining flatter across adulthood (Koster et al., 2020). See Figure 3C. A study of the ontogeny of a number of skills among Tsimane horticulturists found that most skills, including food production, had been acquired by age 20, although self- and peer-ratings of high proficiency in food production for both men and women increased into their 40’s, consistent with the ECM (Schniter et al., 2015). See Figure 3B.

Second, there is increasing evidence that children are able to acquire substantial calories from wild foods (Pretelli et al., 2024). Hadza children, for example, when followed during foraging trips (and not just measuring food returned to camp), often acquired more calories during the day than required by an adult (Crittenden et al., 2013; Froehle et al., 2019). See Figure 3A. A study of child foraging using published data from 28 societies found that their foraging returns, as a fraction

of returns by young adults, increased approximately linearly with age, albeit more slowly for more skill-intensive, difficult-to-extract resources (tubers and game), but more rapidly for easier-to-extract resources (fruit and fish/shellfish) where adult levels of productivity were reached by adolescence (Pretelli et al., 2022).

Figure 3: Age-specific productivity. **A:** Hadza children productivity. Each dot is one foraging trip by one child. Data from Crittenden et al. (2013) and Froehle et al. (2019). **B:** Tsimane female skill acquisition (male skill acquisition is similar). Figure from Schniter et al. (2015). **C:** Age-specific hunting skill. Data and code from Koster et al. (2020). **D:** Age-specific food acquisition skill for the three values of b_1 in Equation 3 that are used in the simulations. See also Table 1.

1.4 Study Aims

Following Gurven & Walker (2005), who took a similar approach to evaluate the energetic consequences of slow vs. fast childhood growth, I will evaluate the energetic consequences of menopause by modeling energy consumption vs. production for a nuclear family comprising the mother, father, and their joint offspring, under the assumptions that mothers do, or do not, experience menopause, but with all other life history, demographic, and energetic factors falling within the ranges typical of contemporary hunter-gatherers. To account for the possibility that skill acquisition was more rapid than proposed in the ECM, I vary the rate over a range of values (Figure 3D).

It should be acknowledged at the outset that, if menopause is an adaptation it co-evolved with demographic and life history factors, so the counterfactual that a species with, e.g., modern human

interbirth intervals, maturation times, body masses, total energy expenditures, and lifespans, but no menopause, is unrealistic. Nevertheless, this exercise could illuminate why it is unrealistic.

2 Methods

Energy balance (production minus consumption) in a hunter-gatherer nuclear family (mother, father, and their joint offspring) was modeled with a discrete time simulation starting at age at first birth (AFB) and continuing with one-year time steps for a maximum modern human lifespan (age 80). All adults reproduce (i.e., no reproductive skew or non-reproductive adults). Mothers give birth at a regular integer-valued interbirth interval (IBI) until the age at last birth (ALB), which is either the end of the lifespan (no menopause) or approximately midlife (menopause). Juveniles mature and leave the family at the AFB. Age- and sex-specific mortality followed standard human life tables. Per capita energy consumption used age-, sex- and body-weight-adjusted total energy expenditure (TEE) values from the literature, which were then summed for all family members. Per capita energy production was based on age- and sex-specific skills and physical strength (proxied by body weight), and varied across a range of parameter values for the relative importance of skill vs. strength, skill acquisition rates, and maximum adult energy production values, which were then summed for all family members. Family energy balance was total family production minus total family consumption computed for each year from the AFB to the maximum age (80). More details on each of these factors is provided in the following sections.

2.1 Age at first birth (AFB), age at last birth (ALB), and interbirth interval (IBI)

Davison & Gurven (2021) compiled demographic and life history values for contemporary hunter-gather populations, small-scale subsistence populations, and chimpanzee populations. I primarily used their averaged values from the five hunter-gatherer populations: Ache, Agta, Hadza, Hiwi, and !Kung (Ju/'hoansi). Although Davison & Gurven (2021) did not provide a numerical value for mean AFB, their Figures 2 and S2 indicate hunter-gatherer values clustering from shortly before 20 years of age to shortly after. They found that the average AFB for all human subsistence populations was shortly before 20 years. Hunter-gatherer age at last birth (ALB) ranged from 36 to 42, with a median of about 38, and mean total fertility was 6.2. Hunter-gatherer IBIs ranged from 2.8 years (Agta) to 3.3 years (Hiwi), with a mean value of 3.1 years. For simplicity, and to match the foregoing values as closely as possible, in all simulation runs fertility was constant until ALB, at which point it was set to 0, IBI = 3 years, AFB = 20, and, for runs with menopause, ALB = 38. Birth at age x was conditional on female survival to age x . For women who survived to the age of menopause, these values resulted in a total fertility of 7, slightly above the mean empirical value. Taking into account that not all women survive to the age of menopause, however, total fertility in the simulations was 6.2. For simulation runs without menopause, women give birth until the end of life.

2.2 Age- and sex-specific survivorship (mortality)

The average life expectancy at birth for human hunter-gatherers of both sexes combined is 30 years (Davison & Gurven, 2021). An analysis of !Kung mortality (Howell, 2017) found that it did not differ meaningfully from other human populations with similar life expectancy at birth

(Coale & Demeny, 1966; Li & Gerland, 2012), a conclusion echoed by Gurven & Kaplan (2007), who concluded that “there is a characteristic life span for our species, in which mortality decreases sharply from infancy through childhood, followed by a period in which mortality rates remain essentially constant to about age 40 years, after which mortality rises steadily in Gompertz fashion” (p. 322).

The Kuhle (2007) hypothesis depends on a sex difference in mortality, which is common in many human populations, as well as in many wild mammals. A study of 101 mammal species, for example, found that the median female lifespan was 18.6% longer than that of conspecific males, and in humans the mean female advantage was 7.8% (Lemaître et al., 2020). For age- and sex-specific survivorship (mortality) I therefore used the data and code from Gaddy et al. (2025), which is based on the UN Model Life Tables (Li & Gerland, 2012). To test the impact of sex differences in mortality combined with a gap in the age of marriage, I used a female life expectancy at birth, $e_0 = 35$, a male life expectancy at birth, $e_0 = 30$, and a sex ratio at birth (SRB) of 1.05 (i.e., a 5% male excess). See Figure 4.

Figure 4: Survival curves. Ache data from Hill & Hurtado (1996). Hadza data from Jones (2016), Kung data from Howell (2017). UN values for female $e_0 = 35$ and male $e_0 = 30$ from UN life tables (Li & Gerland, 2012), using data and code from Gaddy et al. (2025).

2.3 Hunter-gatherer family energy consumption

Total energy expenditure (TEE) is a function of age, body mass, body composition (fat and fat-free mass), and activity levels. Age-related impacts on TEE include the energy required for development, age-related changes in activity levels, and tissue-specific metabolism. For example, the masses of energetically expensive organs, such as liver and brain, comprise a greater fraction of body mass in children than adults. A study of TEE measurements using doubly labeled water (the gold standard method) in a large, diverse sample found four distinct life stages: fat-free mass-adjusted expenditure accelerates rapidly from 0 to 1 year, declines slowly to adult levels by ~20 years, remains approximately stable from 20 to 60, even during pregnancy, and then declines in older adults (Bajunaid et al., 2025; Pontzer et al., 2021).

Somewhat counter-intuitively, after adjusting for age, sex, and body mass, TEE is relatively constant within these four phases, regardless of activity or immune activation. Instead, an individual's fixed energy budget is allocated among, e.g., growth, immunity, and activity. Children in Shuar vs. industrial populations have very similar TEE, for example, but compared to children in industrial populations, Shuar children have higher immune activation and activity, and reduced growth (Urlacher et al., 2019).

Accordingly, hunter-gatherer TEE was modeled using the regression model in Bajunaid et al. (2025), which comprises a linear equation that predicts TEE using age (years), sex, body mass (kg), height (cm), ethnicity, and elevation (m) (see Table 1 in Bajunaid et al., 2025). Body mass and height were modeled as the average of generalized additive models (GAMs) of body masses and heights by age and sex of the Ache, Hadza, and !Kung. Ethnicity and elevation were set as "African" and 1000 m, respectively. See Figure 5. Family energy consumption was the sum of TEE for the mother, father, and their joint children for each age of the mother starting at AFB.

Figure 5: Weight by sex and age (top) and total energy expenditure (TEE) by age and sex (bottom). Female weight and TEE includes pregnancy increase. Kung weight data from Howell (2009). Ache weight data from Walker et al. (2005). Hadza weight data from Jones (2016). TEE values from the equation in Bajunaid et al. (2025).

2.4 Adult hunter-gatherer energy production

A compilation of adult hunter-gatherer energy production by sex found that males typically (but not always) produced a surplus of calories beyond the typical adult male TEE, women generally produced around an adult female TEE (but in some cases with a surplus and in others with a deficit), and the combined male and female production was generally a surplus that would support offspring (Kraft et al., 2021). See Figure 6.

Figure 6: Daily per capita adult energy production by contemporary hunter-gatherer females and males across ten populations. Boxplots in the top panel indicate the distributions of female, male, and total production depicted in the bottom panel. Total (pair bond): average production of one adult female plus one adult male. Grey bars indicate the range of average female (lower) to male (higher) total energy expenditure (TEE) for chimpanzees (left) and adult Hadza (right) measured using doubly labeled water. The dotted line indicates total TEE for one Hadza female + one male. Chimpanzee energy production is assumed to equal total energy expenditure (i.e., no surplus production other than for lactation). Data from Kraft et al. (2021) and Pontzer et al. (2015).

Taking the average daily TEE of a hunter-gatherer adult to be about 2300 kcals, and using the energy production values in Figure 6 from Kraft et al. (2021), adult hunter-gatherer women produced from to - of daily adult TEE, men from to - of daily adult TEE, and one woman plus one man produced from to - of daily adult TEE. Accordingly, maximum female energy production was modeled as a range from 0.4 to 1.8 of adult TEE, and maximum male energy production as a range from 1 to 2.6 of adult TEE, with the constraint that $1.6 \leq TEE_{prop}f + TEE_{prop}m \leq 3.4$ (i.e., the range of surplus to support juvenile offspring).

2.4.1 Age- and sex-specific energy production

Hunter-gatherer energy production (kcal/day) by age and sex is fairly uncertain because there have been very few such populations to study, and measurements might be restricted to food returned to camp (ignoring food consumed during foraging), perhaps obtained only during parts of the year, and/or data from adults only. Drawing inspiration from modeling approaches in Gurven & Walker (2005), Gurven & Kaplan (2006), Koster et al. (2020), and Schniter et al. (2015), I modeled foraging productivity across the lifespan as follows:

$$productivity(age) = TEE_{prop} strength(age)^{\alpha} skill(age)^{1-\alpha} \quad (1)$$

where TEE_{prop} is the proportion of adult TEE, and ranged from 0.4 to 1.8 for women and from 1 to 2.6 for men, and $0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$ is the relative importance of strength vs. skill, and was set to 0.25 (mostly skill-based), 0.5 (equal parts skill and strength), and 0.75 (mostly strength-based),

separately for males and females. Strength was proxied by age- and sex-specific body weight (kg) as a proportion of maximum adult male weight, multiplied by a function that declines rapidly as age approaches the maximum age:

$$strength(age, sex) = \frac{weight(age, sex)(1 - e^{b(age_{max} - age)})}{weight_{max}} \quad (2)$$

where b is a parameter that determines the rate of strength decline in old age, and was fixed at -0.15 for both sexes in all simulation runs.

Skill is the product of a sigmoidal function that predominates at young ages, similar to that fit to the data in Schniter et al. (2015), with a function that declines rapidly as age approaches the maximum age:

$$skill(age) = \frac{1}{1 - e^{-b_1(age - age_{50})}} (1 - e^{b_2(age_{max} - age)}) \quad (3)$$

where b_1 is a parameter that determines the rate of skill acquisition, and age_{50} is the age at which skill is 50% of maximum. These two parameters were combined to create *Fast* ($b_1 = 0.4$, $age_{50} = 10$), *Medium* ($b_1 = 0.25$, $age_{50} = 15$) and *Slow* ($b_1 = 0.15$, $age_{50} = 20$) skill acquisition ontogenies, separately for each sex. b_2 is a parameter that determines the rate of skill decline in old age, and was fixed at -0.15 for both sexes in all simulation runs. Productivity was set to 0 for children less than 3 years old. See Figure 3D and Table 1.

Table 1: Ages at which skill level reaches 50% and 95% of maximum value for each value of b_1 and age_{50} used in the simulations. See Equation 3 and Figure 3 D.

Skill ontogeny	b_1	50%	95%
Fast	0.40	10	17
Medium	0.25	15	27
Slow	0.15	20	40

2.5 Age gaps in marriage

Binford (2001) compiled ages at first marriage from the ethnographic record for men and women in 177 hunter-gatherer societies. The median age difference is 5 years, and the 75% quantile is 9.5 years, so simulations used marriage age gaps of 5 and 10 years. See Figure 7.

Figure 7: Histogram of the mean differences in age at first marriage for husbands and wives in 177 hunter-gatherer societies (positive values indicate older ages for men). Note that these values do not necessarily represent the age difference between spouses because young men’s and women’s first marriages could conceivably have been to much older individuals (which would not be the first marriages for those much older individuals). Data from Marwick et al. (2016).

2.6 Parameter space and simulated life course

One simulation was run for every combination of parameters in Table 2, with the exception that the sum of wife and husband energy production was constrained to $1.6 \leq TEE_{prop}f + TEE_{prop}m \leq 3.4$, as noted earlier. For each of the resulting 9720 combinations of parameter values the following vectors were computed in sequence:

1. wife’s age was an integer-valued vector from AFB until the maximum age (80), at one-year intervals.
2. husband’s age was wife’s age + age gap at marriage.
3. wife’s probability of survival at each age relative to her AFB was computed with the female life table (all wives and husbands assumed to be alive at AFB; with $SRB = 1.05$ the numbers of surviving females and males at AFB is approximately equal).
4. husband’s probability of survival at each age relative to AFB was computed with the male life table.
5. pregnancies (coded as 0, 1) occurred every IBI years, starting at one year prior to AFB.
6. births (coded as 0, 1) occurred every IBI years, starting at AFB and ending at either the age of menopause, or at end of life.
7. child survival was age-specific survival (averaged for females and males) multiplied by births (i.e., no new children in years with birth = 0).
8. wife, husband, and child TEE’s at each age (as described earlier) were multiplied by their survival at each age.
9. wife, husband, and child productivities at each age were computed using Equation 1 and multiplied by their respective survival at each age.

10. total resident children, total resident child consumption, and total resident child production at each wife age were computed assuming children disperse (leave the family) at the AFB, and using a windowing function based on wife's age and wife survival (such that the number of children is scaled by the number of women who survived to give birth; see code).
11. family consumption and production at each wife age were the sums of wife, husband, and total resident children's consumption and production, respectively.
12. family energy balance was family production - family consumption. Neither family member survival, nor pregnancies, births, IBI's, or any other factor was contingent on energy balance. See code for details.

Simulations were deterministic, i.e., there were no stochastic parameters.

Table 2: Parameter values for simulation runs. Each run was a unique combination of these values for each age of women from age at first birth (AFB) to the maximum age (80 years), with the constraint that $1.6 \leq TEE_{prop}f + TEE_{prop}m \leq 3.4$.

Parameter	Description	Values
e_0f	Female life expectancy at birth (years)	35
e_0m	Male life expectancy at birth (years)	30
SRB	Sex ratio at birth	1.05
AFB	Age at first birth (years)	20
age_{max}	Maximum human age (years)	80
Marriage _{gap}	Marriage age gap	5, 10
IBI	Interbirth interval (years)	3
$age_{menopause}$	Age of menopause	38, 80
α_f, α_m	Relative importance of skill vs. strength for females and males	0.25, 0.5, 0.75
$age_{50}f, age_{50}m$	Age of 50% skill acquisition	10, 15, 20
b_1f, b_1m	Skill acquisition rate for females and males	0.15, 0.25, 0.4
$TEE_{prop}f$	Maximum productivity for females as a proportion of adult TEE	0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1, 1.2, 1.4, 1.6, 1.8
$TEE_{prop}m$	Maximum productivity for males as a proportion of adult TEE	1, 1.4, 1.8, 2.2, 2.6

Simulations were conducted using R version 4.4.1 (2024-06-14). Code and data are available here: <https://github.com/grasshoppermouse/menopause>.

3 Results

The main results across the entire parameter space are displayed in Figure S 1. However, not all regions of parameter space are equally plausible for real hunter-gatherer families. For example, in 2513 of 9720 parameter combinations (26%), energy balance was always negative. Most analyses were therefore restricted to a subset of the simulations, as follows. The *Menopause* condition more realistically reflects real hunter-gather families. The restricted subset of simulation runs in the *Menopause* condition comprised those that resulted in mean energy balance values across the entire lifespan that were within 500 kcals of 0. Those in the *No menopause* condition comprised those with combinations of parameter values matching those in the *Menopause* condition. The main results from this subset of 3756 parameter combinations are depicted in Figure 8, which are qualitatively similar to results from the entire parameter space in Figure S 1, albeit with less variation, and biased toward simulation runs with more positive energy balances, although also removing simulations with exceptionally high energy balances.

With the exception that the parameters specifying the joint energy production of wife and husband (TEE_{propf} , TEE_{propm}) were further constrained to a narrow band of higher values, parameter values in the restricted subset nevertheless spanned the entire ranges of possible values, with varying deviations from the equal distributions in the full parameter grid. Specifically, the female skill acquisition rate (b_1f) was biased upwards for higher values of female productivity (TEE_{propf}), and the male skill acquisition rate (b_1m) was biased upwards for intermediate values of male productivity (TEE_{propm}) but downwards for the highest level of male productivity, likely due to the constraint on maximum lifetime energy balance. See Figure S 2.

For wife's age from AFB to age of menopause, during which 0 children are born, the *No menopause* and *Menopause* conditions are identical, after which they diverge. There are only about a maximum of 4 resident children, however, due to child mortality, and to a lesser extent, maternal mortality (Figure 8A).

3.1 Family size

The *No menopause* and *Menopause* conditions diverge at the age of menopause because it is approximately double the AFB, at which point the oldest child leaves the family. In the *No menopause* condition, if there were no mortality, the number of family members would remain constant at around 4 after twice the AFB because as the oldest child dispersed a new child would be born. In the simulations, however, the number of family members, including resident children, slowly decreases in this condition at this age due to maternal mortality that reduces the birth of new children, and husband mortality (Figure 8A, left).

Critically, in the *Menopause* condition, the number of resident children decreases more rapidly after the age of menopause because no new children are born, older children mature and disperse, and child and maternal mortality take their toll, reaching 0 resident children at wife age of 33 (Figure 8A, right). In comparison, 33 year old women in the *No menopause* condition have resident

children, on average. There is no within-condition variation in resident children because no parameter variation impacts IBI, child mortality, or maternal mortality.

3.2 Energy consumption

As family size grows and as children mature, daily family energy consumption grows, and as it shrinks, energy consumption shrinks, but critically, more rapidly in the *Menopause* condition as dispersing offspring are not replaced by new offspring (Figure 8B). There is only minor within-condition variation in energy consumption due to slight differences in husband mortality from the 5 and 10 year age gap.

3.3 Energy production

Family energy production is approximately flat or slightly increasing for about the first decade after AFB, as parents' increasing productivity matches their increasing number of young and maturing children, but then increases in the second decade as parental increases are augmented by the increasing productivity of maturing children. Subsequently, energy production declines due to wife and husband mortality, and in the *Menopause* condition, the departure of older productive children. Within-condition variation is due to variation in the parameters affecting productivity – α , b_1 , and TEE_{prop} – each of which varies by sex. See Table 2. Qualitatively, energy consumption and production track family size.

3.4 Energy balance

For the births of the first two children, mean energy balance (averaging across the restricted parameter space) is positive in both conditions, dropping well below 0 at the birth of the fourth child in both conditions, when, due to child mortality, parents are caring for about 2-3 children. In the *No menopause* condition, mean energy balance is negative after this for the rest of the lifespan (see Figure 8D, left).

In the *Menopause* condition, after menopause (age 32, 38, 44) mean energy balance begins to increase as the productivity of maturing children increases and as children leave the family, becoming positive when wives turn 44 and parents are caring for about 3 children. Energy balance peaks again about a decade later, at age 54, as the last child has left the family, declining thereafter due to wife and husband mortality. See Figure 8D, right.

Figure 8: Simulation results from the restricted subset for the *No menopause* (left) and *Menopause* (right) conditions. Each line in panels B to D represents a result from a run with a single combination of parameter values. Colors in C & D represent the total production of wife and husband as a proportion of adult TEE. Blue lines in C & D are the mean values across all simulations in the subset for each wife age.

Across simulations in the *Menopause* condition with a “Medium” rate of skill acquisition, the proportion of total lifetime energy surplus acquired prior to menopause ranged from 0% to 65%, with a mean of 20%, and correspondingly, the proportion of total surplus acquired post-menopause to the end of life ranged from 100% to 35%, with a mean of 80%.

The influence of parameter combinations on lifetime energy balance in the restricted set of simulations are depicted in Figure S 4. In general, higher joint productivity of the wife and husband

was understandably associated with higher mean energy balance, as was, to a lesser degree, faster skill acquisition by both sexes. In the *No menopause* condition, the combination of these factors in a small region of the parameter space (3.6% of simulations) enabled families with older, productive children to reverse decreasing energy balances. See Figure S 3.

Finally, simulations were also run with an earlier (32) and later (44) age of menopause. At the earlier age of menopause, families start to climb out of the energy deficit earlier and more rapidly (on average), and there is a longer period of energy surplus post menopause, and the converse for the older age at menopause. Other than the ages of menopause, these simulations used the same parameter values as used in the primary set of simulations. See Figure S 6. With earlier and older ages of menopause, total fertility is lower or higher (+/- 2 births). A future analysis would seek the values of the IBI, lifespan, age at first birth, body size (TEE), and so forth, that optimize fitness, given, e.g., abilities to extract energy from the environment.

3.5 Parent mortality

Mortality of both wives and husbands is high. At age 50, 60% of wives have survived, and 46% of their older husbands have survived. Only about one parent, on average, thus remains to care for a mean 1.5 older children in the *Menopause* condition (ages 12 and/or 15), whereas in the *No menopause* condition, one parent would be caring for a mean of 3.5 children, some probably quite young (e.g., 2, 5, and 8).

4 Discussion

The key insight from the simulations is that without menopause, and given the energy consumption and production rates of contemporary foragers, the modern human pattern of relatively short interbirth intervals, long periods of juvenile dependency, minimal reproductive skew, and long lifespans, could not have evolved. At the third or fourth birth in most simulations, parents with several highly dependent offspring would not be able to feed them (Figure 8D, left, but see Figure S 3).

The energetic crisis is averted by ceasing reproduction midlife combined with increasing juvenile productivity and energy transfers. Even though the simulations did not include energy transfers between nuclear families, the family energy surpluses that were present at some life stages in most simulations, could be transferred to families in energy deficit at other life stages. Indeed, this was one rationale for restricting analyses to those with mean lifetime energy balances close to 0: energy surpluses in some life stages would be sufficient to offset energy deficits in other stages via energy transfers between nuclear families. These results are broadly consistent with Kaplan et al. (2010) (compare Figure 8D, left, with Figure 2C,D), albeit with important distinctions noted below.

To rule out the viability of a human-style life history sans menopause, it is important to consider that in the first three years, before the birth of the second child, 89% of the parameter combinations in the restricted parameter space had positive energy balance in at least one of those years, with a median surplus of 726 kcals. Because infants and young children require 400-1300 kcals/day, the surplus would be enough to support one additional young child beyond the nuclear family.

Although this degree of energetic subsidy would be sufficient to support reproduction (and therefore lifespan) into the wife's early-to-mid thirties when she would have about 3 dependent offspring, the family would then experience an energy deficit from which, absent menopause, they could not recover.

The simulations therefore suggest the following role of menopause in the co-evolution of modern human life history traits. Shorter interbirth intervals and longer periods of juvenile dependence sow the seeds of a mid-life energy crisis: families have produced many young offspring with high energy requirements but who, per the ECM, require many years to acquire the skills necessary to provision themselves. Parents averted this crisis with three evolved strategies. First, by ceasing the production of new offspring in midlife (menopause), around age 40, parents' energetic investments would then go solely to offspring whose increasing skills enabled them to begin supporting themselves before their dispersal, at which point parents began climbing out of an energy deficit even without subsidies (Figure 8D, right). This would have been especially effective if offspring skill acquisition was relatively rapid (see the b_1 panels in Figure S 4). This refocuses the mother hypothesis on the energy production capacity of the mother, father, and their older offspring.

Second, young adults with only one or two children produced a surplus that subsidized their immature siblings to whom they are as closely genetically related as to their own offspring, akin to the "helper at the nest" pattern seen in some other cooperatively breeding species (Hagen & Barrett, 2009; Hatchwell, 2009). This is consistent with the brideservice practices of many hunter-gatherer societies in which the bridegroom works for the bride's family in exchange for marriage; brideprice is a related practice in which the bridegroom's family pays the bride's family with some form of wealth (Goody & Tambiah, 1973; Walker et al., 2011). Third, older parents, perhaps especially the wife's parents (Daly & Perry, 2017), produced a surplus that subsidized their younger adult children's children (the grandmother hypothesis, albeit here also including the grandfather) because the older parents' one or two dependent older children largely supported themselves or perhaps even produced a surplus, or their children have all dispersed.

4.1 Rethinking the father absence hypothesis to include mother absence

Kuhle (2007) proposed that menopause might have evolved to mitigate the negative consequences of higher paternal than maternal mortality. At age 50 in a species with menopause, a surviving parent would be caring for one or two older children, whereas without menopause it would be 3 or 4 children, some quite young. It is possible that limiting the childcare burden on a surviving parent to a few older dependent offspring, which probably would have been manageable, rather than the care of several younger ones, which probably would not have been manageable, was a selection pressure for menopause. However, because the death of the wife would also have been common, and because the fitnesses of monogamous parents is tightly coupled, it is *parental* absence, not necessarily father absence, that matters. (As an aside, the not infrequent death of mothers with multiple dependent children could have helped select for female fidelity to ensure fathers would continue to invest in their joint offspring.)

4.2 Rethinking menopause and the ECM

There are three important distinctions between the results of the simulations reported here, and the Kaplan et al. (2010) “two sex” model. First, Kaplan et al. (2010) emphasize the importance of the increasing costs of pregnancy and childbirth with increasing age: in their model, menopause evolves because at midlife these costs reduce the benefits of continued reproduction which then no longer outweigh the benefits of transferring resources to kin. In the simulations, in contrast, menopause evolves simply because, given the amounts of energy that foragers can extract from environment, the relatively rapid production of offspring who require substantial calories yet who cannot support themselves for a decade or more, limits their number to about four. This limit is reached after 6-7 births spaced 3 years apart (with high infant mortality), i.e., about 20 years after age at first birth. Nevertheless, age-related increases in the costs of pregnancy and childbirth could be additional factors favoring menopause.

Second, juvenile productivity plays little role in the Kaplan et al. (2010) model but an important role in the simulations, where, in combination with reproductive cessation, the increasing productivity of older juveniles (Pretelli et al., 2024, 2022) helps families escape an energy deficit even without energy transfers (but energy transfers from young adults and older parents are still critical).

Third, although I have framed the simulations in terms of nuclear families comprising a wife and husband in a lifelong monogamous relationship raising their joint offspring — a key assumption of Kaplan et al. (2010) — the results of the simulations do not rely on this assumption. The results are equally consistent with, e.g., a pooled energy model (Kramer & Ellison, 2010) in which all females reproduce (i.e., no non-reproductive females) and all individuals pool their resources to provision every member of the community according to their needs. The potential midlife energy crisis is simply a consequence of producing offspring every three years who require substantial calories to reach adulthood yet cannot provide all those calories themselves for a decade or more. In this regard, results are also consistent with the venerable grandmother hypothesis (Hawkes, 2020). Note, however, that the simulations do not address the collective action problems or other evolutionary challenges of energy transfers. They also do not take into account that in real families and communities, parents and children adjust the time devoted to production in response to changes in demand (e.g., Kramer, 2005).

Although ceasing reproduction midlife and transferring energy surpluses are key to averting an energetic crisis, the increasing productivity of dependent offspring is also key. Yet in mobile hunter-gatherers ranging over a large, spatially and temporally varying landscape replete with competitors, predators, and other sundry hazards (e.g., Jones et al., 1994), child productivity in ancestral foraging bands would have depended on foraging bands moving to the right place at the right time (Bettinger & Grote, 2016; Hamilton et al., 2016). Embodied capital should therefore be conceptualized not only as the skills required to extract energy from a resource patch, but also as including the skills required to locate optimal resource patches.

Older mothers and fathers would have had greater knowledge of the large ranges necessary to support the hunting and gathering lifestyle of a large-bodied hominin (Antón, 2002), and hence greater ability to lead their families to productive resource patches, a perspective that aligns with

theories of menopause in toothed whales that emphasize the superior ecological knowledge of matriarchs (Rendell et al., 2019). It is also consistent with the anthropology of older women in traditional societies who increasingly take on important social roles (Brown, 1982; Jang et al., 2025), with research on the important ecological knowledge of older individuals in foraging societies (e.g., Biesele & Howell, 1981; Scalise Sugiyama, 2011; Wiessner, 2014; Wood et al., 2024), and with the computational services model, which emphasizes the cognitive challenges of raising multiple dependent offspring (Hagen et al., 2025).

5 Concluding remarks

Simulation results do not illuminate why the distinctive human life history pattern evolved (see, e.g., Kaplan et al., 2000). They do suggest, however, that menopause was an integral element of this distinctive pattern, necessary to avert a midlife energetic crisis threatened by relatively short interbirth intervals and long periods of dependency of large bodied and large brained, and thus energetically expensive juveniles. Young couples, who in ethnographically documented hunter-gatherers often lived with either the wife's or husband's parents (Hill et al., 2011), produced an energetic surplus, likely subsidizing the younger siblings of the wife or husband via, e.g., brideservice (Walker et al., 2011). Couples' midlife reproductive cessation (menopause) optimized family size at an energetically sustainable level as juvenile energy production ramped up (a variant of the mother hypothesis, albeit here also including fathers and older offspring), and energy transfers from couples' parents increased (the grandmother hypothesis, albeit here also including grandfathers). The couple and their increasingly productive offspring (Pretelli et al., 2024, 2022) then became energetically self-sustaining, and finally energetically "profitable", with the capacity to invest in their children's families.

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7 Supplementary information

Figure S 1: Results from all simulations for the *No menopause* (left) and *Menopause* (right) conditions. Each line in panels B to D represents a result from a run with a single combination of parameter values. Colors in C & D represent the total production of wife and husband as a proportion of adult TEE. Blue lines in C & D are the mean values across all simulations for each wife age.

Figure S 2: Heatmaps of $(Observed - Expected)/Expected$ for every combination of parameter values in the restricted subset of simulations compared to the unrestricted set. -1: no simulations with that combination; 0: the expected number of simulations; 1: twice as many simulations as expected; 2: 3x as many simulations as expected. Grey: missing in the original parameter grid due to the constraint: $1.6 \leq TEE_{prop}f + TEE_{prop}m \leq 3.4$.

Figure S 3: Example trajectories from the small region (3.6% of simulations) of the restricted parameter space in the *No Menopause* condition in which energy balances were positive. Columns: $TEE_{prop}m$. Rows: b_1m . For clarity, the parameter space is further restricted to: $TEE_{prop}f = 1$, $Marriage_{gap} = 5$, and $alpha_m = alpha_f = 0.5$.

Figure S 4: Relationship between parameter combinations and mean lifetime energy balance in the set of simulations with lifetime mean energy balances restricted to those within 500 kcal of 0. See also Figure 8.

Figure S 5: Relationship between parameter combinations and mean lifetime energy balance in all simulations. See also Figure S 1.

Figure S 6: Mean energy balance in simulations with multiple ages of menopause but with all other parameters assuming the same values as in the main analysis. Numeric values are total fertility, taking into account female mortality. Menopause age 38 corresponds to the *Menopause* condition in the main analysis, and Menopause age 80 to the *No menopause* condition.

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